

Foster Forest: A Game to Imagine the Forest of the Future

Introduction

How can forests be managed in a context of increasing climate change, with increasingly diverse social, economic, and environmental interests? How can understanding be fostered between forest managers, political representatives, private landowners, and environmental advocates? Foster Forest, a participatory simulation game, proposes innovative answers to these questions.

An Innovative Tool for Climate Adaptation

Foster Forest is much more than a game. It is a simulation tool that allows participants to step into the shoes of different stakeholders involved in forest management and explore—through rounds of decision-making and simulated outcomes—how their actions

could affect forests in the coming decades. This immersive experience offers a safe space for trial and error, dialogue, and joint solution-building.

The dynamic combines the use of forest simulation software with role-playing. Each participant takes on the role of a key actor: public forest managers, private landowners, political representatives, or environmental organization members.

Over several rounds of play, they must make decisions about their forest plots: plant or cut? Certify? Protect? Sell? Change land use?

The system automatically calculates the ecological and economic effects of each action. Budgets are updated based on costs and revenues, and environmental indicators—such as stored carbon, water quality, or landscape popularity—evolve based on collective decisions.

Figure 1: Static Foster Forest model. Copyright : Revue Forestière Française

Three Acts for a Collective Experience

The Foster Forest workshop is structured in three main phases:

- **Introduction:** Each participant's role is explained, along with their goals (budgetary, ecological, or social), possible actions, and available information: timber prices, climate projections, interactive maps with forest inventories, soil quality, or conservation-eligible areas.
- **The Game:** Each round simulates a decade, starting in 2020. Participants decide actions such as hunting leases, natural or artificial regeneration, logging, certification, conservation of mature forests, plot exchanges, etc. After each round, the system updates indicators and presents the consequences. A facilitator guides the session and addresses unexpected proposals if they've been pre-coded (e.g., public awareness campaigns).

- **Final Discussion:** The workshop concludes with a 50-minute group discussion where participants share impressions, analyze strategies, and reflect on the climate scenario. This is a key moment to foster empathy, understand different viewpoints, and open conversations about the future of forests.

A Transferable Innovation

Although Foster Forest was initially developed within the EUROFORNORM operational group in Normandy, its design is adaptable to other regions. The initial research-oriented version has been simplified to make it more accessible as an awareness-raising tool. It now includes collective options such as carbon storage payment programs, citizen awareness campaigns, wood origin labels, and assisted species migration. Freely available at www.fosterforest.fr, the software includes video tutorials and documentation to facilitate its implementation.

Figure 2: Foster Forest workshop procedure. Copyright : Revue Forestière Française

While some parameters are calibrated for French forests, the approach is replicable in any country that values dialogue, experimentation, and co-creation of forest futures.

Playing for Change?

Foster Forest proves that games can be serious tools. By combining simulation, participation, and reflection, it enables different actors to experiment, negotiate, and better understand the challenges of forest management in the face of climate change. And in the process, it plants seeds of adaptation, collaboration, and real transformation.

Further information

[Know more about EUROFORNORM Operational Group Informative video](#)

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Funded by the European Union (Grant n. 101086216). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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